

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

STUDY OF HEAT AND ELECTROPHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF SYSTEM ALLOYS $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{B}_2\text{O}_3 - \text{Nd}_2\text{O}_3$

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7139804>

**Bananyarli S.,
Ismayilov Sh.,
Khalilova L.**

*named after academician M.Naghiyev
Institute of Catalysis and Inorganic Chemistry,
Baku, H.Javid str., 113*

Abstract

Thermal and electrophysical properties of several samples selected from the studied system $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{B}_2\text{O}_3 - \text{Nd}_2\text{O}_3$: dependence of electrical conductivity on temperature and field frequency. It was found that the electrical conductivity of the samples increases with increasing temperature and shows semiconducting properties. The semiconducting properties of these samples are explained by the presence of Nd^{+3} and Bi^{+5} ions. It is known that the Nd and Bi element atoms are involved in the formation of donor-acceptor bonds. An increase in temperature activates the energy levels in the samples and they participate in the electrical conductivity. Also, as the temperature increases, the additional potential fields created by the boron, neodymium, and bismuth ions in the composition are different, so the carriers falling into their fields behave like polarons.

Keywords: resistance, ligand centers, Nd_2O_3 , electrical conductivity, frequency, semiconductor, thermal conductivity, heat resistance, phonons, polarons.

Introduction

Chemical resistance, mechanical strength, easy obtaining of technologically suitable materials have increased the demand for new materials based on inorganic oxides in electronics and various fields of technology. The study of $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{B}_2\text{O}_3 - \text{Nd}_2\text{O}_3$ system alloys we have studied is similar. We have studied the electrophysical properties of some sections of the triple system $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{B}_2\text{O}_3 - \text{Nd}_2\text{O}_3$ [1-3]. The aim of this work is to discover new materials that can be used in electronics, radio engineering and in the manufacture of converters operating at different frequencies. Thus, these system alloys can also play a role as an active dielectric material in the manufacture of capacitors or converters of different frequencies [4-6]. Neodymium borates are promising for high-frequency fields of electronics and technology [6-10].

The experimental part

Chemically pure Bi_2O_3 , H_3BO_3 and Nd_2O_3 reagents were used in the synthesis of samples for the study of the $\text{B}_2\text{O}_3 - \text{Nd}_2\text{O}_3$ system. The synthesis was carried out at a temperature of 1000-1100°C for 8 hours. The synthesized samples are yellow polycrystalline substances. The experiments were performed on corundum crucibles.

Electrophysical properties were studied in the temperature range $T = 300-800\text{K}$. An electrometer B7-

30 was used to determine the resistances and at the same time it was checked by the resonance method using a Tesla BM-560 device for comparison. The difference between the measured values was about 4.0%. Differential thermal analysis (DTA) NETZCHSTA 449F3STA - 0836 - Conducted on M derivatograph.

Results and their discussion

$\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{B}_2\text{O}_3 - \text{Nd}_2\text{O}_3$ cross section №1 (95 mol% $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{B}_2\text{O}_3 - 5$ mol% Nd_2O_3); The temperature dependences of their resistance were measured first of all from the electro-physical properties of samples containing №3 (85 mol% $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{B}_2\text{O}_3 - 15$ mol% Nd_2O_3). The results are shown in Figure 1. Sharp anomalous changes in the temperature dependence of the resistances of the samples were observed. Their $\rho(T)$ dependences can be divided into three temperature ranges:

1. In the temperature range $T = 300 \div 420\text{K}$, the $\rho(T)$ dependence of sample №1 decreases very weakly and smoothly. Sample №3 is stable.
2. In the temperature range $T = 460 \div 520\text{K}$, the resistances of both samples decrease by passing through the extremum.
3. At $T \geq 520\text{K}$, an exponential decrease in the resistance of both samples is observed in semiconductors.

Figure 1. Temperature dependence of resistance in samples 1 and 3.
 1-95 mol% $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{B}_2\text{O}_3 - 5\text{mol}\% \text{Nd}_2\text{O}_3$;
 3-85 mol% $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{B}_2\text{O}_3 - 15\text{mol}\% \text{Nd}_2\text{O}_3$

Deviations from the regularities observed in the dependence of $\rho(T)$ may be due to the non-statistical distribution of ligand centers in the synthesized samples. Breakthrough changes were observed depending

on the frequency of the field of electrical conductivity of the samples. The results obtained are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Field frequency dependence of electrical conductivity of samples 1 and 3.
 1-95 mol% $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{B}_2\text{O}_3 - 5\text{mol}\% \text{Nd}_2\text{O}_3$;
 3-85 mol% $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{B}_2\text{O}_3 - 15\text{mol}\% \text{Nd}_2\text{O}_3$

As can be seen from the graphs, the values of electrical conductivity vary at different frequencies in the field. However, as the frequency increases, the conduction mechanism of both samples increases. The reason for the semiconducting properties of these compounds is the presence of Nd^{3+} and Bi^{5+} ions. The atoms of this element create the acceptor and donor energy levels, which are partially located deep. As the

temperature increases, these energy levels become active and they participate in the electrical conductivity. In the samples, the electrical conductivity increases with increasing temperature and the semiconductor property is shown. The activation energy of the carriers of the studied samples was determined. The results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1.
 Activation energy of samples 1 and 3.

№	Compositions	T=300 ÷ 500K		T ≥ 500K	
		$\sigma = \sigma_0 \cdot T^n$	activation energy (eV)	$\sigma = \sigma_0 \cdot T^n$	activation energy (eV)
1	95 mol% $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{B}_2\text{O}_3 - 5\text{mol}\% \text{Nd}_2\text{O}_3$	$T^{0,2}$	0,54	$T^{0,44}$	2,00
2	85mol% $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{B}_2\text{O}_3 - 15\text{mol}\% \text{Nd}_2\text{O}_3$	$T^{0,42}$	0,74	$T^{0,78}$	2,05

As can be seen from the table, $T = 300 \div 500$ K varies with the law $\sigma \sim T^n$ ($n \approx 0,2 \div 0,45$) in the temperature range and $\sigma \sim T^n$ ($n \approx 0,44 \div 0,82$) in the temperature range $T > 500$ K. Accordingly, the activation energy of the carriers also increases proportionally as the amount of Nd_2O_3 oxide in the composition increases. This is explained by the fact that the energy levels of the carriers are located at different depths and their activation varies with increasing temperature. As can be seen from the table, the electrical conductivity of these samples increases weakly in the temperature range $T = 300 \div 500$ K. At $T > 500$ K it is relatively intensive.

Figure 3 shows the temperature dependence of the thermal conductivity of these samples (Figure 3). As can be seen from the graphs, the value of the total thermal conductivity coefficient decreases with increasing

temperature. In samples №2 and №3, this decrease is partially monotonous. In Example 1, in the temperature range $T = 380 \div 500$ K varies anomalously. A monotonous decrease is observed in the subsequent increase of temperature. As can be seen from Figure 3, in samples №1 at $T > 500$ K, the value of χ drops sharply. Note that the electrical conductivity in the studied samples is very low. It can be assumed that the total thermal conductivity in these alloys is approximately equal to the structural one ($\chi_t \approx \chi_{st}$). The change in the thermal conductivity values is entirely related to the defective structure of the samples. The thermal conductivity in sample №1 in the range $T=300\div 450$ K changes according to the law $\chi \sim T^{-0.83}$, and at $T > 500$ K $\chi \sim T^3$. In samples №2 and №3 at temperatures of $300\div 450$ K $\chi \sim T^{-0.01}$, and at $T > 500$ K $\chi \sim T^{-0.2}$.

Figure 3. Temperature dependence of thermal conductivity of components 1,2,3
 №1 -95mol% $Bi_2O_3 \cdot B_2O_3 - 5mol\%Nd_2O_3$;
 №2 -85 mol% $Bi_2O_3 \cdot B_2O_3 - 15mol\%Nd_2O_3$
 №3 -85 mol% $Bi_2O_3 \cdot B_2O_3 - 15mol\%Nd_2O_3 \cdot B_2O_3$

In order to determine the defective nature of the components, the temperature dependences of their thermal resistance were considered. Figure 4 shows the $\omega = f(T)$ dependencies of these samples. (Figure 4)

Figure 4. Temperature dependences of heat resistance.
 №1 -95mol% $Bi_2O_3 \cdot B_2O_3 - 5mol\%Nd_2O_3$;
 №2 -85 mol% $Bi_2O_3 \cdot B_2O_3 - 15mol\%Nd_2O_3$
 №3 -85 mol% $Bi_2O_3 \cdot B_2O_3 - 15mol\%Nd_2O_3 \cdot B_2O_3$

As mentioned above, since the electrical conductivity of these compounds is small, the total thermal conductivity can be taken to be approximately equal to the thermal conductivity of the cage.

$$\chi_t \approx \chi_c (\chi_{i.c.} = 0)$$

In this case, the inverse value of the thermal conductivity of the cage can be taken equal to the thermal resistance. The temperature dependence of the thermal resistance assessed by this method is shown in Figure 4. As can be seen from the figure, the temperature coefficient of thermal resistance $1 / \chi_c \approx \omega$ for all three substances changes (increases) linearly at a temperature $T = 300 - 440$ K. However, in the subsequent increase in temperature, deviations from this line are observed. These deviations are due to the additional scattering of carriers from polar optical phonons. As the temperature increases, the additional potential fields created by the different amounts of boron, neodymium, and bismuth ions in the composition are different, so the charge carriers falling into their fields behave like polarons. For this reason, the linear increase in thermal resistance is violated. It is likely that because the ions in these compositions have different valences, the polarization cre-

ated by such centers will also be different, and scattering from polarized optical phonons will also have different effects on the change in χ .

Temperature dependence of thermal conductivity of samples №2 60 mol% $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{B}_2\text{O}_3 - 40\text{mol}\%$ $\text{Nd}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{B}_2\text{O}_3$ and №3 50mol% $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{B}_2\text{O}_3 - 50\text{mol}\%$ $\text{Nd}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{B}_2\text{O}_3$ were studied. The aim is to discover the role of the Nd and B elements in heat transfer. It is known that the neodymium element and the Nd^{3+} ion conduct electricity and heat better than the boron element. Boron is a pure dielectric material: although it conducts heat very poorly, B^{3+} ions, on the other hand, form a dense alloy by trapping inter-atomic voids in the alloy, and are also partially heat carriers relative to the voids. It is in the set of generally opposite characteristics that the total thermal conductivity has a certain value. The temperature dependences of the total thermal conductivity of these compounds decrease with increasing temperature. As can be seen from the graphs, the $\chi = f(T)$ dependence of sample №3 decreases relative to sample №2 by exceeding the maximum at temperature $T = 380 - 460$ K. It is assumed that this anomalous change is due to the change in optical polarization in the sample due to the activation of Nd^{3+} ions with increasing temperature.

Figure 5. Temperature dependences of ω – thermal resistances of samples №2 and №3.
 2- 60mol% $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{B}_2\text{O}_3 - 40$ mol% $\text{Nd}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{B}_2\text{O}_3$
 3- 50mol% $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{B}_2\text{O}_3 - 50$ mol% $\text{Nd}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{B}_2\text{O}_3$

Figure 5 shows the temperature dependences of the thermal resistances of these samples. As mentioned above, the thermal resistance of the components is very sensitive to their defective nature. The dependence $\omega = f(T)$ usually increases linearly, and the total thermal resistance varies as $\omega = \omega_0 + AT$. Here, ω_0 characterizes the additional thermal resistance that occurs when an additional additive is introduced, and this quantity does not depend on σ . As can be seen from the graphs, the thermal resistance due to this additional detection is in the order $\omega_0 = 75 \text{ Sm} / \text{vt} \cdot \text{k}$ in sample №2, and in the order $\omega_0 = 64 \text{ Sm} / \text{vt} \cdot \text{k}$ in sample №3, as well as in both samples $\omega = f(T)$. Deviations from linear dependence were observed. This deviation is greater in example №3.

Results

1. As the temperature increases in the samples, the energy levels generated by the Nd^{3+} and Bi^{5+} ions are activated, the electrical conductivity increases, and the semiconductor property is shown.

2. The activation energy of the carriers increases in proportion to the increase in the amount of Nd_2O_3 oxide in the samples studied. This is explained by the fact that the energy levels of the carriers are located at different depths and their activation is different with increasing temperature.

3. As the temperature rises, the carriers behave like polarons. For this reason, the linear increase in thermal resistance is violated. Probably because the ions in these compositions have different valences, the polarization created by such centers is also different, and scattering from polarized optical phonons also has a different effect on the change in χ .

References:

1. S.I.Bananyarli, Sh.S.Ismayilov, R.N.Gasimovam, L.A.Khalilova. Study of $3\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 5\text{B}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{Nd}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{B}_2\text{O}_3$ system and dependence of electrophysical and heat properties of obtained alloys on the composition. Chem.Probl. 2020. №1. p.106-112.
2. S.I.Bananyarli, R.N.Gasimova, Sh.S.Ismayilov, L.A.Khalilova, I.F.Mehdiyeva. $3\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 5\text{B}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{Nd}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{B}_2\text{O}_3$ system and electrophysical properties of intermediate alloys. Конференция Научные Исследование XXI века : Теория и практика. 2018. г. Прага. Чехия. с 24-31.
3. S.I.Bananyarli, Sh.S.Ismayilov, N.V.Chernisheva. Electric and thermal properties of disordered alloys on the basis of Bi and Nd borates. Chem.Probl. 2013. №2. p. 270-273.
4. В.В.Пасынков, В.С.Сорокин Материалы электронной техники. М.Высшая Школа. с.366
5. В.В. Пасынков, Л.К. Чиркин Полупроводников приборы. Санкт – Петербург. Москва. 2006. с.479.
6. А.И. Лебедев Физика полупроводниковые приборы. Москва “Физматлит” 2008. с.478.
7. Д. Карфут Введение в физику сегнетоэлектрических явлений. М. изд. “Мир”1972. с. 352.
8. А.Т. Шиваев, В.Г. Власенко, Д.С. Дранников, И.А. Зарубин. Структура и диэлектрические свойства $\text{Bi}_4\text{Pb}_{1,5}\text{Ti}_{4,5}\text{O}_{16,5}$ и $\text{Bi}_5\text{Ca}_{0,5}\text{Ti}_{3,5}\text{O}_{16,5}$. Неорганические материалы. 2005. Том 41. №10. с. 1231-1235.
9. О.А. Гудаев, В.К. Малиновский Электропроводность полярных неупорядоченных материалов при многофоновых переходах. ФТТ. 1992. Т. 34. №2. с. 548 – 553.
10. Н. Мотт, Э. Девис. Электронные процессы в некристаллических веществах. Москва: Мир. 1982. Т.1. с. 368.